

IMPERIAL

Aeronautics

Overcoming Processing Hurdles in Multifunctional Polymers & Polymer (Nano)Composites

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Unlocking Materials Properties/Applications

Easy to Process / Low Costs /
Environmentally Benign

<https://www.euractiv.com>

Multifunctional

Environment/Fracture/
Fatigue/Damage/Fire
Tolerant

Integrated Sensors

Integrated Energy
Storage/Harvesting

Integrated Actuators

Processing Hurdles

1. Dispersion of (nano)particles

2. Microstructure Control

3. Limited Processing Window

High Processing Temperature/Pressure

Low Thermal Stability

High Viscosity

Conductive Carbon Nanoparticles

Carbon Nanotubes (CNT)

Graphene

Young's Modulus = 1 TPa
 Tensile Strength = 100 GPa
 Electrical Conductivity = 10^5 - 10^7 Sm⁻¹

CNTs - Low Percolation Threshold, p_c

$$\sigma = \sigma_0(p - p_c)^t$$

$$p_c \propto \frac{1}{\text{Aspect Ratio}}$$

Typically well below 1 wt% CNTs !

Percolation of polymer/CNT (nano)composites

Percolation of polymer/CNT (nano)composites

Compression Moulded Films Vs Compounded Pellets

Matrix: TPU
Estane[®], Lubrizol (USA)

Filler: MWNT
NC7000, Nanocyl (Belgium)

Non-equilibrium system!

Dynamic Percolation

Controlling (Dynamic) Percolation

Predictive Model for Conductivity of Polymer / CNT melt-spun filaments!

Assumption:

Conductive network formation is governed (or is limited) by the polymer matrix viscosity, a first order thermally activated phenomenon.

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta t} \propto \frac{1}{n_0}$$

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma_T}{\Delta t_T} \propto 1/\exp\left(\frac{\Delta E}{RT}\right)$$

$$\Delta t'_{T^*} = \Delta t_T \exp\left(\frac{\Delta E}{RT^*}\right) / \exp\left(\frac{\Delta E}{RT}\right)$$

Analogy with the time-temperature superposition

Bilotti *et al.* J. Mater. Chem., 2010

Strain Sensing

PU / MWNT

Zhang *et al.* Phys. Rev. B 2007

Strain Sensing

Tensile Strain Sensing in textiles

FP6 Project INTELTEX

Compressive (Force) Sensing in shoe insoles

Naderizadeh *et al.* IEEE Sensors, 2023

NURVV | RUN

Degradation Sensing

PLA/CNT in Water at 50 °C

- Resistivity decreases upon degradation.
- The composite with a CNT loading around the percolation threshold gives the highest sensitivity and strongest signal change.

M. Fang *et al.* Polymer 2013

Pyroresistivity

Liu *et al.* Polym Int. 2019; 68: 299–305

Pyroresistivity – Temperature Sensing / Self-Regulating Heating

Smart/Safe Heaters

Low temperature (comfort/sensing) (led by Dr. Yi Liu, Loughborough Uni)

High temperature (for curing) (led by Dr. Han Zhang, Warwick Uni)

WO2016012762; PCT/GB2015/052073

Y. Liu *et al.* Adv Funct Mater 2018

Y. Liu *et al.* JMCC 2018

Guo H. *et al.* Adv Funct Mater 2025

Y. Wang *et al.* ACS AMI, 2023, 15, 48, 56265

Graphene

Folding, scrolling, etc.

Kalaitzidou et al., Compos Part A, (2007).

Even on solid substrates...

On Mica

On PVA

On PMMA

Graphene

Layer-by-Layer deposition PVA/GO

150 bi-layers transparent in visible light (85% @ 550 nm)

New Strategy

Inspired by "Nature": LbL

- Via Solution
- Slow
- Thin films
- Requires good dispersion/suspension of nanoflakes

Sellam *et al.*, Nanocomposites (2015)

Inspired by ...

- Via Melt
- Fast/Continuous process
- Bulk

Pressing & Folding (P&F)

Technique to study/design nanocomposites as a function of filler dispersion

Puff-pastry preparation technique

Santagiuliana et al., ACS Nano 2018

Pressing & Folding (P&F)

LLDPE + 5 v% Graphite NanoPlatelets (GNP)

The higher the number of P&F cycles the better is the dispersion of GNP in the polymer matrix and the higher is the anisotropy

Pressing & Folding (P&F)

LLDPE / GNP

@ 5 v% GNP

Young's Modulus and Tensile Stress increase with number of P&F cycles

@ 200 P&F cycles

No loss of reinforcing efficiency at ultra high V_p !

Santagiuliana et al., ACS Nano 2018

Pressing & Folding (P&F)

Does it work so well for other polymers or nanofillers?

Nanoparticle “Distribution Rates”: “I”

	graphite	EG	xGNP750	TRGO	MMT
LLDPE	$7.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$
HDPE	-	$9.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	-
Phenoxy	-	$0.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	-
PC	-	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	$0.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$
TPU	-	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	-

LLDPE + 70 vol.% MMT

$$E_C/E_M=11$$

(=2 for melt compounding)

Santagiuliana et al., ACS Nano 2018

Energy Storage - Polymer Dielectric Capacitor

PVDF

- Lower β phase content above T_m
- γ phase in lower M_w PVDF above T_m
- PVDF with higher M_w exhibits >90% β phase content when P&F at 180°C

Meng et al., Nature Comm. 2019

PCT/GB2020/050034

Energy Storage - Polymer Dielectric Capacitor

Average crystallite size

- Enhanced β phase content
- Reduced crystallite size
- Internal stress build-up

Meng et al., Nature Comm. 2019

PCT/GB2020/050034

Energy Storage - Polymer Dielectric Capacitor

PCT/GB2020/050034

Ren et al. Nano Energy, 2020 104662

Ren et al. J. Mater. Chem. A, 2022, 10, 10171

Energy Storage - Polymer Dielectric Capacitor

CNT Veil electrodes assembly

Rolling

Pressing+60 °C Annealed

PCT/GB2020/050034

Ren et al. Nano Energy, 2020 104662
Ren et al. J. Mater. Chem. A, 2022, 10, 10171

Silk Fibres

Nephila spider dragline silk

Degummed silk worm silk fibre, spun by the animal at different spinning rates

Silk Cocoon - Protective shell.

Bombyx Mori

Primary function: Protect the vulnerable pupa from physical damage and predation during metamorphosis = **Stiffness/Toughness.**

In Compression!

Additional functions: Thermal insulation; Moisture control; UV shielding

Titan OceanGate submersible disaster 2023

Guo et al. Nature Mater. (2020)
 Shao et al. Nature. (2002)
 Vollrath, Knight. Nature (2001)

Silk Fibre – ‘Spun by Nature’

Silk Glands

Spinning duct

In-glands silk processing via:

- Silk dope acidification
- Concentration change of metal ions
- Water content reduction

- ✓ Low temperature
- ✓ Low energy
- ✓ Water-based

Liquid crystalline behaviour

- ✓ Intractable

Aramid fibres

Toh et al. Prog. Polym. Science (2015).

Vollrath, Knight. Nature (2001).

From Fibres to Bulk artifacts?

However:

- Loss of hierarchical structure and properties
- 'One shot' only

Silk 'Regeneration'

ARTICLES

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-019-0560-8>

nature
materials

Thermoplastic moulding of regenerated silk

Chengchen Guo^{1,2}, Chunmei Li^{1,2*}, Hiep V. Vu², Philip Hanna³, Aron Lechtig^{1,3}, Yimin Qiu¹, Xuan Mu¹, Shengjie Ling^{1,4}, Ara Nazarian^{3,5}, Samuel J. Lin⁶ and David L. Kaplan^{1*}

Guo et al. Nature Mater. (2020).

'All-Silk Composites' / 'Self-reinforced silk composites'

Heat + Pressure

Heat + Pressure

Publication Under Revision

'All-Silk Composites'

< 215 °C,
No change in:

- Conformation (β -sheet/ α -helix/random coil),
- Crystallinity or
- Orientation of Silk fibres

Publication Under Revision

'All-Silk Composites' – Flexural Properties

Publication Under Revision

Fracture Toughness

Gas gun Ballistic tests

Publication Under Revision

'All-Silk Composites' – Other Functionalities

Tuneable in-vitro/in-vivo Degradation

Optical Properties

Triboelectric Nanogenerators

(Collaboration with Dr. Andris Sutka (RTU))

Self-Healing

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ICCCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

THANK YOU

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Energy Harvesting – Organic Thermoelectrics

Lycra® / Na_x(Ni-ett)_n

Wan et al., Adv Electr Mater 2019

Lycra® / PEDOT:PSS 10/90 films

Taroni et al., Adv Funct Mater 2017

Integration of Functionalities

'All-Silk Composites' – Mechanism

Publication Under Revision

'Degumming' efficiency

Sericine removal for:

- Increased mechanical properties
- Improved biocompatibility

Picric acid/Carmine staining.
Under alkaline conditions, silk fibroin only adsorbs picric acid (yellow) and silk sericin adsorbs also carmine (red)

Publication Under Revision

'Degumming'

No loss in mech properties

'All-Silk Composites' – FTIR Analysis

No change in β -sheet/ α -helix/random coil up to 215 °C

Publication Under Revision

'All-Silk Composites' – 1D WAXD

No change in degree of crystallinity up to 215 °C

Publication Under Revision

'All-Silk Composites' – 2D WAXD

Little to No change in crystal orientation up to 215 °C

Publication Under Revision